

LECTURERS' PERSONALITY AND MANAGERIAL SKILLS IN SHAPPING ENTERPRENEURIAL CHARACTERISTICS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study intends to examine the effect of personality, managerial skills on the entrepreneurial characteristics of lecturers at Universitas Labuhanbatu. This research was conducted at Universitas Labuhanbatu. The research population was all lecturers at Universitas Labuhanbatu amounted 121 lectures. The data were collected by using questionnaires. A total of 121 questionnaires were distributed and returned 111 questionnaires. Therefore, the participants in this present study amounted to 111 lecturers. The research approach was a quantitative approach. The data analysis technique used structural equation modeling, the data was processed using AMOS software version 23. The results showed that the data in the study were normally distributed and had met the goodness of fit test. The results of hypothesis testing indicate that personality affects a lecturer's managerial skills positively and significantly. Lecturer's entrepreneurial characteristics can be influenced by personality and managerial skills.

Keywords: Personality, Managerial Skills, Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

1. INTRODUCTION

Universitas Labuhanbatu is one of the universities in Labuhanbatu Regency with a vision to become a university that produces creative and independent graduates based on entrepreneurship at the national level in 2033. Therefore, lecturers with a high entrepreneurial spirit are expected to achieve this vision. In the achievement of the University's vision in 2020 makes the Business Incubator Unit, but unfortunately, the business incubator that was established is not active and does not exist entrepreneurial activity generated. The number of lecturers who have a business-only about 10 lecturers has a business and this is dominated by a lecturer at the Faculty of Law where the lecturer has a profession as a Notaries, Lawyers, and Experts.

Entrepreneurship is one concrete step to get out of the problem of the relevance of education and other ways education provides value add to national productivity (Hasanah, 2019). An entrepreneur is a process of applying creativity and innovation in solving problems and finding opportunities to improve business life (Zimmerer, 2008). Entrepreneurship consists of edupreneurship, which is a creative and independent business by seeing or creating opportunities and realizing them into something that has added value. Lecturers who have an entrepreneurial spirit are called teacherpreneurs, while teacherpreneurship is entrepreneurship that carried out by lecturers (Mauluddin and Eko, 2017). Lecturers are one of the main components in order to achieve learning objectives and increase competence in the world of education. Law No. 14 of 2005 states that professional lecturers are lecturers who are able to

act as educators, instructors, mentors, directors, trainers, assessors and evaluate students according to the expertise of the lecturer. The main task of the lecturer is to carry out the tri dharma of higher education, namely teaching, research, and community

Service so that lecturers are able to develop creativity, innovation, and social skills (Efendi & Nuraeni, 2020). The challenge of educational professionalism in today's global era is that lecturers must be able to innovate and be creative in the learning process. This attitude can be found in entrepreneurs (Wisnu and Hermin, 2016).

Based on the background that has been presented previously, the researcher is interested in further researching the influence of the lecturer's personality and managerial skills on the entrepreneurial characteristics of lecturers at Universitas Labuhanbatu.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Characteristics of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is an attitude that shows courage in taking risks and also creating value (Pranowo et al, 2020). Cultivating an entrepreneurial attitude in education is called entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship consists of school entrepreneurship (school), technopreneurship (students), and teacher entrepreneurship (teacher/lecturer). Cultivation of attitude teacher entrepreneurship on lecturers can be done through a leadership process transformational so that it raises the productivity of the lecturer in work (Jamal, 2017). Teacherpreneur is a lecturer who has a soul Entrepreneur. Teacherpreneurship always innovates to improve the quality of learning through research activities and policy formulation. He be a leader for their students. Work done then published to increase their achievement scores (Effendi and Nuraeni, 2020).

Entrepreneurial values are prerequisites related to entrepreneurial behavior (Frederick et al., 2006). These values consist of creativity, risk-taking, innovation, achievement-oriented, ambition, and independence Boohene et al. (2008). Values in running a business contain an element of consideration that develops the ideas of a personal or social person, so it is preferred over the form of behavior or the final form of the existence of resistance or kindness.

2.2 Personality

According to Kreitner and Kinicki (2010) personality is defined as a stable combination of physical and mental characteristics that give an individual identity. These characteristics or traits or traits include how people see, think, act and feel, which are the product of genetic interactions and environmental influences. Another opinion suggests that personality is a relatively enduring pattern of thought, emotion, and behavior that shows the characteristics of people, in line with the psychological processes behind these characteristics (McShane and Von Glinow, 2010).

Meanwhile, Robbins and Judge (2011) state that personality is a dynamic organization of

psychological systems within an individual that determines his unique adjustment to his environment. It is also said that personality is the sum of all the ways in which individuals react to and interact with other people. Meanwhile, according to Colquitt, LePine and Wesson (2011), personality shows the structures and tendencies in people that explain their characteristic patterns in thinking, emotion, and behavior.

Another opinion states that personality means how people influence other people and how they understand and see themselves, as well as their patterns of inside and outside measurable traits and person-situation interactions (Luthans, 2011).

Personality is a relatively enduring pattern of ways that a person feels, thinks, and behaves. Personality is an important factor in accounting for why employees act the way they do in organizations and why they have favorable or unfavorable attitudes towards their jobs and organizations. Personality has been shown to influence career choice, job satisfaction, stress, leadership, and several aspects of job performance (George and Jones, 2012).

2.3 Managerial Skills

Managerial skills include planning and organizing, identifying customers and distribution channels, managing resources and capabilities set up in the right place, and system structure control. These skills include high-level skills, such as seeking problem-solving, the ability to build core skills and the ability to handle employees effectively. One of the dimension of the goal in entrepreneurship education is to increase the ability of students (Eman, 2010). According to Kandou et al (2016) entrepreneurial character is influenced by aspects of managerial skills, technical skills, and entrepreneurship skills. According to the opinion expressed by Winardi (2010) states that "Managerial ability is the ability to take actions planning, organizing, implementing, monitoring carried out to achieve the goals that have been set.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted with a quantitative method approach. The research was conducted on Lecturers at Universitas Labuhanbatu. The total population are 121 lecturers. The research sample is determined by looking at the provisions of the structural equation modeling method, which is a minimum of 100 samples. The questionnaires were returned by 111 respondents. So that the sample in this study amounted to 111 people. This study uses three variables, namely the entrepreneurial characteristics of the lecturers, the personality of the lecturers, and the skills of the lecturers.

4. FINDING

4.1 Normality test

Normality test is one of the classical assumption tests that must be met in structural equation modeling. A normality test needs to be done to find out whether the research data comes from a normally distributed population. The provisions of the normality test on the structural equation modeling by looking at the

skewness and kurtosis, which are between -2.58 to 2.58 (Schumacker & Lomax, 2010).

Table 1. Normality test

Variable	skew	cr	kurtosis	cr
Y5	-.934	-4.018	1,601	3,442
Y4	-.651	-2,798	.093	.200
Y3	-.777	-3.341	.398	.855
Y2	-.973	-4.187	1,565	3.366
Y1	-.977	-4,200	.934	2008
X1.1	-1.075	-4.625	1.446	3.109
X1.2	-1.060	-4.561	1.252	2,692
X1.3	-.895	-3,851	.976	2,100
X1.4	-.829	-3.566	1.055	2.269
X1.5	-.864	-3.718	1.158	2,489
X2.5	-.433	-1.861	-.448	-.963
X2.4	-.464	-1,996	-.203	-.437
X2.3	-.470	-2.022	.184	.395
X2.2	-.692	-2,978	.850	1,828
X2.1	-.801	-3.447	.524	1,128
Multivariate			9.139	2,132

The table above shows that the multivariate cr value is 2.132. This value is in accordance with the recommended value, which is between 2.58. Thus it can be concluded that the distribution of the data used in the study is normally distributed.

4.2 Model Fit Test

Table 2. The Goodness of Fit Test of the Model

The Goodness of Fit Index	Result	Decision
Cmin/DF	1,680	Good Fit
Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI)	0.796	MarginalFit
The goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.852	Good Fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.950	Good Fit
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	0.939	Good Fit
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.079	Good Fit
Root Mean Square Residual (RMSR)	0.035	Good Fit

Table 2 above informs that all criteria have been met in accordance with the values recommended by Hair et al, (2013). Thus, it can proceed to the next stage.

4.3 Hypothesis test

The hypothesis in this study consists of testing teacher personality on teacher managerial skills. Testing teacher managerial skills on the entrepreneurial characteristics of lecturers, then testing the influence of the lecturer's personality on entrepreneurial characteristics. All hypotheses in this study were accepted. This can be seen from the critical ratio value > 1.96 and a probability level of <0.05 (Byrne, 2010).

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing Result

			Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
Teacher_Management_Skil	<---	Teacher_Personality	0.857	.129	8089	0.000	Supported
Teacher_Entrepreneurship_Characteristics	<---	Teacher_Management_Skil	.548	.154	3.356	0.000	Supported
Teacher_Entrepreneurship_Characteristics	<---	Teacher_Personality	.371	.180	2,373	0.018	Supported

Goodness of Fit Test
 Chi-square = 146.146 ;df = 87; p = .000 ;CMIN/DF = 1.680 ;RMSEA = .079
 ;RMR = .035 ;GFI = .852 ;AGFI = .796 ;CFI = .950 ;TLI = .939

Figure 2. The Full Model of Research

4.4 Discussion

Thus the first hypothesis in this study is accepted.

A lecturer who has an entrepreneurial spirit will certainly show more creativity and innovation in carrying out his/her duties as a lecturer. Some of the characteristics of lecturers who have entrepreneurial characteristics such as having high achievement motivation, having a commitment, having innovation, having an ethos, and being responsible at work.

The results showed that all hypotheses in this study were accepted. This means that personality and managerial skills can improve the level of entrepreneurial characteristics. The first hypothesis in this study is that there is an influence between the lecturer's personality on managerial skills. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that the influence of the lecturer's personality on managerial skills has a critical ratio (cr) value of 8089 and a significance value of 0.000. The critical ratio is greater than 1.96 ($8,089 > 1.96$) and the probability value is < 0.005 ($0.000 < 0.05$).

This means that the personality of the lecturer is proven to influence the managerial skills of the lecturer. This means that the better the lecturer's personality in carrying out his duties, the better the entrepreneurial spirit of the lecturer will be. On the other hand, if the lecturer's personality is not good, then the lecturer's entrepreneurial spirit will be lower. The research

findings are in accordance with the results of research conducted by (Aprillianita et al., 2020) who found that soft skills were one of the building blocks of the entrepreneurial spirit. Soft skills in question can be emotional intelligence, personality, social skills, communication, friendliness, and optimism.

The second hypothesis in this study is that there is an influence between managerial skills on entrepreneurial characteristics. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that the effect of managerial skills on entrepreneurial characteristics has a critical ratio (cr) value of 3.356 and a significance value of 0.000. The value critical ratio is greater than 1.96 ($3.356 > 1.96$) and the probability value is < 0.005 ($0.000 < 0.05$).

Thus the second hypothesis in this study also can be accepted. This means that the managerial skills of lecturers are proven to influence the entrepreneurial characteristics of lecturers. The second hypothesis in this study is that there is an influence between personality on entrepreneurial characteristics. Based on the results of testing the third hypothesis, it shows that the influence of personality on entrepreneurial characteristics has a critical ratio (cr) value of 2.373 and a significance value of 0.018. The critical ratio is greater than 1.96 ($2.373 > 1.96$) and the probability value is < 0.005 ($0.018 < 0.05$). Thus, the third hypothesis in this study is accepted. This means that the lecturer's personality is proven to have an influence on the entrepreneurial characteristics of lecturers at Universitas Labuhanbatu.

5. CONCLUSION

The results show that the lecturer's personality and managerial skills can shape the lecturer's entrepreneurial spirit. This shows that a good lecturer's personality and good managerial skills will make lecturers have more entrepreneurial characteristics, for example, more motivated, innovative, and creative in carrying out their duties as lecturers.

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